

D5.2 Concept (business) plan for post-project sustainability

Grant Agreement Number	825640
Project Acronym	DIHNET.EU
Deliverable Date	7 December 2021
Authors	Kristina Karanikolova, Maurits Butter (TNO)
Number of Pages	21
Number of Annexes	0
Version	1
Reviewed by	Ruud Baartmans (TNO), Marta Palau Franco
Approved by	Ruud Baartmans (TNO)
Dissemination level	Public

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under grant agreement No 825640.
www.dihnet.eu

Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to analyse the DIHNET assets and activities with the aim to identify possible sustainability plans for the individual aspects. Based on the analysis, we can conclude that one of the main assets and key to the DIHNET has been the development of an active community. This has been supported by all activities of the DIHNET project.

An important outcome of the analysis is that in the last years of work has been that the ecosystem is still developing. The upcoming Digital Transformation Accelerator (DTA) and EDIHs are expected to be the backbone of the EU DIH ecosystem. Also, the DTA is expected to offer services close to the activities of the DIHNET but focused on EDIHs. As a result, and given the fact that this network is not yet operational, DIHNET has decided to continue with the DIHNET community and social media outreach (albeit on a limited intensity of activities) until the DTA is selected or up to 6 months after the end of the DIHNET project. This will allow the relevant partners to leverage on the momentum and the DIHNET brand while also leaving the flexibility to re-evaluate the future options for the community after the new network is in place. This position will ensure that in the meantime, the EU DIH Community still has a point of contact until the next network is established.

The deliverable dives deeper into the DIHNET services and assets and the overview below provides an outline of the sustainability plans per particular activity. These conclusions are based on an overall analysis of DIHNET added value, the customers of DIHNET as well as how DIHNET adds value through assets and services. To give an example, the DIHNET community will be continued by FBA but other activities like the overview of open calls will be stopped. More details can be found in the conclusion.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary.....	2
1 Introduction	5
1.1 Introduction to the report and DIHNET project	5
1.2 Mission and objectives of the future DIHNET	6
1.3 Main impacts and results of DIHNET so far	6
1.4 Changing context and connection to other networks	7
1.4.1 The DTA.....	7
1.4.2 The EDIH strategy.....	7
1.4.3 Networks explicitly supporting collaboration (especially in widening regions) - The BOWI examples.....	8
1.4.4 EEN and clusters.....	8
1.4.5 EIT- European Institute of Innovation & Technology.....	8
1.4.6 Concluding: changing ecosystem in the EU DIH universe.....	8
1.5 The future of the DIHNET network and connection to future DTA	8
2 'Customers' of the DIHNET network	9
2.1 Direct customers	9
2.1.1 DIHs, CC, candidate EDIHs	9
2.1.2 DIH networks.....	9
2.2 Indirect customers	9
2.2.1 European Commission.....	9
2.2.2 Regional policy makers.....	10
2.2.3 Regional innovation stakeholders	10
2.2.4 Other networks (non DIH specific)	10
2.3 Concluding: diverse customer group with societal mission	11
3 Assets of the DIHNET network	11
3.1 Introduction to the key assets.....	11
3.1.1 DIHNET community.....	11
3.1.2 DIHNET brand.....	12
3.1.3 Tools and approaches developed.....	12
3.1.4 Information and materials.....	13
3.1.5 Team and community expertise.....	13

4	Services to support the network of networks	14
4.1	Overall introduction of the services of the DIHNET network	14
4.2	Ecosystem development services	14
4.3	Business development services.....	15
4.4	Skills development services and resources	15
4.5	Technology development services	15
4.6	Connecting the services and interest from customers	15
5	Possible options to sustain DIHNET project assets and activities.....	16
5.1	Setting up a separate association/legal entity	17
5.2	DIHNET public materials and deliverables.....	17
5.3	Invite the DIHNET community to the future DTA community and handover of lessons learnt 18	
5.4	Continuation of the activity led by a partner	18
5.5	Stop activity and engagement.....	19
5.6	Summary and overview of post-project plans for the different assets and activities	20
6	Conclusions	20
6.1	DIHNET community, brand and communication	21
6.2	Open access to (main) DIHNET outputs and documents.....	21
6.3	Hand-over lessons learned to DTA and reference of the community	21

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the report and DIHNET project

The objective of this deliverable is to explore a light plan for the post-project sustainability of DIHNET and its assets. This work is part of the WP5 exploring post-project sustainability with the aim to draw conclusions on a way forward to the future DIHNET network. Based on the consortium current view on the EU DIH ecosystem, it is our view that some of the assets of DIHNET should be continued at least until the upcoming DTA and its plans to support the (E)DIH network are clear. The deliverable presents a concept plan, which will need to be further evaluated depending on the context in which the DIHNET network will continue to operate.

DIHNET project aims to help the development of a network of networks. DIHNET supports the collaboration among networks of DIHs in Europe. The project provides tools and mechanisms to encourage cooperation, discussion and alignment in the DIH ecosystem.

The DIHNET project aims to create a network of networks of DIHs and with this provide support and coordination in the EU DIH ecosystem. Within the project, different tools have been used to initiate discussions, to align and inspire the thinking on collaboration in the DIH universe as well as to support stakeholders in finding each other and initiating a discussion in various groups. Examples of some of the activities include the work on initiating discussion on strategic topics (like specialization, DIH ecosystem, post-project sustainability) in a thought leadership programme, starting various working groups on common challenges, including the pre-cursor EDIH network, an active community of over 1500 members, events and webinars, champion challenge of DIHs and monthly DIH rubric, connection and cross-dissemination with DIH related initiatives. With this, the DIHNET has built a brand in the ecosystem as trustworthy and forward-looking community.

After three years the DIHNET project is coming to an end. The network has been initiated and activated. This deliverable therefore assesses which DIHNET assets, activities and project results can be sustained and how selected elements can be continued after the project. In this regard, this deliverable forms a light sustainability model of the project.

It should be highlighted that the DIH ecosystem has recently changed and new initiatives – such as the Digital Transformation Acceleration – and new horizontal collaboration networks have emerged. This has put into question the viability of sustaining a horizontal network such as the DIHNET. Therefore, in the deliverable we will also explore the possibility of other networks continuing (some) activities – e.g. the DTA – and we have chosen to explore the possibilities for sustainability per asset and drawing conclusions on possible interdependencies after that.

After short introduction of the overall context of DIHNET and its objective, the paper will discuss 1) who are the customers benefiting from the added value of the DIHNET 2) how is value added through the DIHNET activities and assets, 3) possible options for sustainability of different elements and 4) conclusions on the way forward.

1.2 Mission and objectives of the future DIHNET

The mission of (post-project) DIHNET is to offer tools and support alignment and collaboration among members of the EU DIH community so they can better cooperate, make use of each other's capacities and improve their support to the European industry on digitalization.

It is the DIHNET consortium belief that by supporting the alignment and collaboration in the DIH ecosystem, the

network of networks can be strengthened, contacts established and as a result stakeholders can better make use of each other's capacities and expertise resulting in better support for the EU industry.

DIHNET is doing this by initiating and supporting discussions, supporting networking and promoting and supporting collaboration. Each of these activities are supported by a community platform, collection of materials, articles, good practices and references to relevant information in the ecosystem. Further, strategic discussions have been supported via events and webinars as well as working on common topics in sub-groups (like working groups). The resulting understanding of the needs, challenges and opportunities have also been communicated to policy makers via regular interaction, events and DIHNET's deliverables and papers.

Figure 1: DIHNET mission and objectives, 2021

1.3 Main impacts and results of DIHNET so far

The overall mission of the DIHNET has been to support the EU DIH community. During the project, various tools and activities have been developed and through them, it is the consortium believe that, DIHNET has activated the individual stakeholders in the community and opened a discussion channel. This in turn, has led to more contact and willingness to cooperate and a more coherency in the ecosystem. DIHNET has contributed to this by the:

- Creation of a network-of-networks of Digital Innovation Hubs to stimulate cooperation and alignment on common topics. Connection with networks - (AEDIB) and EBN and many more- have been initiated, connecting the various stakeholders.
- Reinforced links with other initiatives, supported by regional, national and European stakeholders (e.g. clusters) by participation in joined events on the roles of such initiatives.
- Offering a vision and contributing to the understanding of (E)DIH/DIH network services and function of the different actors, thereby improving the discussion as well as indirectly the services in the ecosystem
- Enhancing the sustainable European collaboration between the different DIHs. This is done in three ways. Firstly, by providing opportunities and tools to find each other (e.g. via the

DIHNET community with over 1600 members). Secondly, by enabling the learning between hubs via sharing good practices through the champion challenge and the DIH of the month and thirdly by engaging the ecosystem to exchange of opinions in events and working groups.

1.4 Changing context and connection to other networks

The DIHNET project is at its end and an evaluation of its position in the ecosystem is in order. It should be noted that so far, DIHNET has fulfilled the purpose of a horizontal network, connecting other DIH networks and offering support and initiating strategic discussions. Yet, such a position is difficult to sustain and is very much dependent on the future development of the ecosystem and its needs. Therefore, the next sections aim to address the changing ecosystem in which DIHNET exists and how this affects the sustainability plans.

1.4.1 The DTA

With the Digital Europe Programme, the upcoming Digital Transformation Accelerator (DTA) is expected to support and coordinate the network of about 200 EDIHs and also connect to the existing DIH ecosystem. The DTA – together with existing thematic and national networks – is expected to be the main coordination body of DIH ecosystem in Europe. Many of the anticipated activities of the DTA – such as the networking and peer exchange – aim at aligning the network. In this respect, lessons learned and the community of DIHNET and especially the precursor network are clear assets that could be of interest to DTA.

This coordination role of the DTA and the envisioned activities are however – to a certain extent – overlapping with the mission and activities of horizontal networks like DIHNET. This poses a challenge for the sustainability of DIHNET.

1.4.2 The EDIH strategy

EDIHs are expected to be key stakeholders but will be coordinated by another entity – DTA. In that sense the EDIHs expand/widen the DIHNET target group and the DIHNET has so far aimed to address and initiate discussion on these new entities and their relation to the current ecosystem.

EDIHs can be seen as regional gatekeep/connection which can connect the regional stakeholders to European stakeholders. The role of EDIHs will vary across regions depending on the local situation. Some will be just established, others would transform from an existing DIHs, and some would be a cooperation of existing DIHs.

With this new entity, we also see a change of the DIH ecosystem and need to further clarify the responsibilities and roles of the different entities (CCs, DIHs, EDIHs, networks). DIHNET has started an informal precursor EDIH network with about 70 participants to discuss the EDIHs and their role. A paper with an analysis and recommendations from this group was presented to the EC and also in the GEARING UP event in 2021.

The challenge for the DIHNET is that the EDIHs have not yet been selected and the coordination DTA project is still to be formed. With that in mind, it is difficult to make a plan for a possible collaboration.

1.4.3 Networks explicitly supporting collaboration (especially in widening regions) - The BOWI examples

We can observe that many networks are nowadays supporting cross-border collaboration with the help of DIHs and these networks are developing collaboration and cooperation tools for a particular sector but also the ecosystem at large. Some examples include the Innovation Actions (e.g. in robotics) but also the BOWI project aims to support the establishment of structural corridors among hubs in Europe, with particular focus on connecting widening regions with the rest of Europe.

The BOWI network has developed tools and approaches to support establishing connections such as the heatmap (allowing DIHs to map their specialization along technology and sector). DIHNET has cooperated with BOWI on the transversal topics (like the dissemination and feedback on the heatmap). However, establishing structural collaborations among individual members is not part of the DIHNET objective. Rather DIHNET aims to elevate the discussions and learn from the experience, and raising awareness of networks which can use the BOWI approach. This function can however also be adopted by the future DTA which will have the specific objective of setting up collaborations. In this sense, a close collaboration is needed by the future DTA and initiatives similar to BOWI.

1.4.4 EEN and clusters

The EEN network connects member state (MS) representatives and businesses across Europe. The EEN is already an established and working network and as such the EEN services should also be considered by the (E)DIHs to be incorporated or connected to their portfolio. Cooperation with the EEN, other thematic networks and the DTA and alignment of services and responsibilities is needed to ensure efficiency of operations in the future EDIH network. Naturally, this connection should also extend to DIHs.

1.4.5 EIT- European Institute of Innovation & Technology

EIT nodes sometimes can be seen as DIHs and sometimes as partners within DIHs depending on the regional situation. EIT topical networks also present a coordination body (e.g. on manufacturing or digital). Therefore, coordination of activities and cooperation for the future is important with this network.

1.4.6 Concluding: changing ecosystem in the EU DIH universe

Based on the above analysis, we observe that the EU DIH ecosystem is changing and adapting. Cooperation and alignment need to still be supported to stimulate and find areas of collaboration and alignment of responsibilities in the network. We see a number of networks and they each have a specific function and add value to the network. Exchange of information, cooperation and alignment should however be continued to ensure that the stakeholders can clearly see to which network they can address specific questions and to limit the potential overlap of activities while maximizing access to each other's capacities.

1.5 The future of the DIHNET network and connection to future DTA

Mission of the DIHNET network is to support collaboration and alignment in the EU DIH ecosystem. Yet, we can envision that this mission will partially overlap with future DTA and other networks.

Therefore, to avoid duplication of effort, DIHNET suggests to continue with the DIHNET community with reduced activity for up to 6 months after the project and then re-evaluate whether and how the community could be continued based also on the activities of the DTA (which we expect will be selected by then). DIHNET therefore suggests to consider individual assets and think how these could be sustained, instead of continuing all activities.

2 'Customers' of the DIHNET network

2.1 Direct customers

2.1.1 DIHs, CC, candidate EDIHs

Competence Centres (CCs), Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and candidate European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIHs) can be seen as a primary direct customer of DIHNET. These actors are often part of various networks on regional but also EU level. As such, they often need support with coordination and discussion on common topics to enable peer exchange.

To address these needs, DIHNET has offered a community with collection of good practices (e.g. monthly DIHs is featured) and opportunities to connect and network in the community and the DIHNET events. DIHNET has also strived to offer ideas and vision on the developments in the ecosystem and roles in the ecosystem, thus stimulating discussion on commonly identified topics. In addition, DIHNET offered (in or view) relevant information and updates (community collections, news, events, common community space).

2.1.2 DIH networks

We also observe in the recent years that many networks have emerged to support the cooperation among DIHs in specific sectors or on specific technologies. Yet, alignment and common discussions on strategic topics is also needed at the level of networks in order to exchange information, good practices, but also to address overall topics such as future connection of networks with the EDIHs or how can such networks support industry and the DIHs.

DIHNET has aimed to address these networks and develop a network of network in order to provide this forum for exchange and discussion among the various networks. Some of the example activities include the initiation of developing a vision with networks like RODIN, working with the JRC on ideas on how to improve the JRC Catalogue in addition to the support provided to evaluate entries, monthly connection and publishing of news from connected DIH initiatives, the initiation of working groups on common topics, but also cross-participation in events of connected networks and vice-versa networks participating in DIHNET events. These activities have all aimed to support the community of networks and to stimulate alignment and common language and understanding among the stakeholders.

2.2 Indirect customers

2.2.1 European Commission

The European Commission has been supporting the DIH development and thinking since 2016 by developing supportive policies as well as with various projects supporting the establishment and

running of hubs in different sectors. With the Digital Europe Programme and the introduction of the EDIHs, this role is further strengthened. The EC is continuously supporting the development and alignment in the DIH ecosystem (provided via various CSAs and IAs at the moment). But policy makers also can make use of input from DIHs and networks on the needs of the ecosystem as well as industry. Such input could support the discussions and policy development for the future.

To support the later, DIHNET has aimed to identify common needs and questions (thought leadership), providing connection on the needs and vision of the ecosystem back to the EC. To support alignment in the ecosystem, DIHNET is focused on supporting a community where stakeholders can find each other – also in sub-networks – supporting networking via WGs and events, as well as gathering of news and open calls from connected initiatives.

2.2.2 Regional policy makers

Regional policymakers can also be seen as a separate customer group as they are part of the overall context in which a DIH acts. Therefore, regional policy makers participate in forming a view of the network and the needs (and understanding their role). But the reverse is also true – the DIHs can offer a deeper understanding of the local needs to regional policy makers.

DIHNET has aimed to improve the understanding of the role of DIHs to regional policy makers (see D1.3) as well as to highlight the connection to the regional stakeholders to DIHs and other networks.

2.2.3 Regional innovation stakeholders

Other regional stakeholders like clusters, development agencies, industry associations often form part of the DIHs and other networks. Yet, they are also a separate 'customer' for networks like DIHNET where the stakeholders can exchange ideas on responsibilities in the EU ecosystem, connection and future development. One way in which DIHNET has addressed this customer group is to offer the opportunity for opening sub-spaces as well as to highlight the different roles and possible complementarities for collaboration in the regional level.

2.2.4 Other networks (non DIH specific)

Other networks such as the EEN and even networks of RTOs or business-oriented networks like EIT could also be considered a secondary indirect customer of DIHNET. Digital Innovation Hubs have become an important mechanism to support organizing the (regional) ecosystems and connecting relevant stakeholders and supporting digital uptake. This makes them an attractive partner for various (non-DIH) networks which would like to partner or connect to the DIHs and their regional stakeholders.

Establishing a link between the different groups could add value to both - the DIH could benefit from access to a new partner (with particular assets and knowledge which could be useful in informing/connecting their customers) and the networks connects to the DIH and through it, its stakeholders. DIHNET has aimed to initiate a discussion on the connection between DIHs, DIH networks and other networks in different workshops – one such example was the final event where a vision of the EU DIH ecosystem for 2030 was outlined.

2.3 Concluding: diverse customer group with societal mission

DIHNET aims to support the network of DIH stakeholders in Europe. This includes direct and indirect 'customers' with different needs and expectations towards DIHNET. One thing that most of these target groups have in common though is their societal mission and activities. We see this in the CC which aim to support the technology base in Europe and are often involved in DIHs to support the further development and adoption of innovation. Similarly (E)DIHs orchestrate the regional ecosystems, connecting the local stakeholders and supporting the translation of innovation into business opportunities. Policy makers (at all levels) aim to provide the right framework conditions for innovation and collaboration and existing networks add value via various services either directly to industry or through collaboration in entities like DIHs.

This societal mission of the DIHNET 'customers' allows DIHNET to gather interest and support in the collaboration and support activities. But this function of the 'customers' also has impact on their readiness to pay for some horizontal activities (discussed further in the next chapter).

3 Assets of the DIHNET network

3.1 Introduction to the key assets

The assets of the DIHNET network leverage on the assets developed in the DIHNET project. The DIHNET project assets can be divided into 5 main categories: 1) the DIHNET network and community, 2) the DIHNET tools and approaches developed, 3) the information, materials and outputs from the DIHNET project, 4) the DIHNET brand and corresponding trust in the DIHNET activities, 5) the expertise and experience of the consortium and the network contributing the above elements.

3.1.1 DIHNET community

One of the key assets of the DIHNET project is the strong community of over 1500 members (registered in the DIHNET community). Members of the DIHNET community include: DIHs, representatives of other DIH-related initiatives and projects (e.g. I4MS, SAE, etc). The community has been steadily

growing and attracting new members. Within the project, joining the DIHNET community has been available for free.

The DIHNET community is supported by the FBA community platform. The main purpose of the community is to provide a place/tool for members (mostly (E)DIHs and DIH networks) to find each other and connect. Further the community acts as an awareness and interest creation tool. Community space is free for registration and provides access to community generated news, events, collections of public articles, etc

3.1.1.1 *Sub-networks and the precursor EDIH network*

Sub-communities and networks have already been initiated as part of the DIHNET project. These could be continued in the future as long as the community platform is continued. Some of the sub-networks are self-guiding and self-activating. These basically use the DIHNET IT community platform to arrange and discuss among themselves.

But there are also groups (WGs, the precursor network, etc) in which the DIHNET project consortium has taken an active moderating role. Our experience is that in such groups, there is a need for a leader of the discussions. However, many of the topics of interest in these WGs are horizontal (relating to many networks) and are expected to be addressed by the future DTA. Therefore, our suggestion is that as long as the DIHNET community platform is open (re-evaluation suggested 6 months after end of the project), the initiated WGs and communities will remain open. However, the activation efforts will be limited from the DIHNET consortium.

3.1.2 DIHNET brand

DIHNET project has managed to establish a brand of the DIHNET community, associated with inclusion, leading discussions and expertise. This is evidenced by the activity and size of the DIHNET community and the popular attendance of DIHNET events.

The developed brand can therefore also be leveraged on to attract new members and continue the discussions in the ecosystem. As a consequence, FBA which hosts the community platform has decided to continue operations of the DIHNET community with the same name for 6 months upon which time re-evaluation will be made. In this period, FundingBox and, on a voluntary basis, other partners will continue feeding the community with relevant information of interest for networks and DIHs such as funding opportunities, events, etc. FBA will keep inviting the members to use it as a central dissemination point for DIHs. We can expect that the DIHNET activity will slightly decrease but possibility to inform the community and to engage by sharing news and even materials, would exist. This will also allow time to evaluate how the ecosystem will settle with the upcoming newly established networks (or ERA hubs and DTA for example).

3.1.3 Tools and approaches developed

DIHNET has developed a number of tools and approaches to support the ecosystem. Several can be highlighted:

- Champion challenge and the identification of good practices
- Working Groups and sub-communities as a way to engage different parts of the community
- Precursor network and related sub-groups

- Thought leadership approach allowing for (co-)development opportunities of a vision or view on particular aspects in the EU DIH community as well as an opportunity to share challenges and opportunities with the EC and therefore support the policy debate;
- Tools to support the community in their JRC Catalogue application (both information as well as offered pre-check).

These approaches offer good practices which have initiated and included the community in various activities and discussions. Therefore, these could be considered an asset for DIHNET as well as a lesson learned for other and new initiatives.

3.1.4 Information and materials

DIHNET project has in its lifetime provided various materials and information to the community in the form of reports, presentations, webinars, etc. These constitute a rich source of information and within the project have served as the basis to initiate strategic discussions with the community and policy makers. Some examples include the papers on the building blocks of the EU DIH ecosystem, specialization and collaboration and the role of DIHs, the view on improving the JRC Catalogue, the co-developed advice and reflections from the precursor network, etc.

Next to the above papers, the community has also gathered information on:

- Articles and opinions shared by the consortium, the DIHNET Ambassadors and DIHNET Advisory Board
- News, events and pieces of information from related initiatives which were collected and shared with the community via a monthly curated news collection
- A collection of DIHs of the month, representing good practices across Europe, as well as information on connected projects
- Collection of various trainings from other projects as part of the community Academy.

It is the consortium view that this collection of materials is a key asset of the DIHNET network as it represents a source of information and showcases the expertise (in the case of DIHNET papers or presentations) of the consortium as well as the broad ecosystem connected to the community (in the case of news contributions in the community).

The materials should therefore be sustained – which we have chosen to do by publishing content on the community and selected materials in Zenodo platform and the website. But this asset needs to be continuously developed if it is to continue to add value in the future.

3.1.5 Team and community expertise

One of the key assets of the DIHNET project has been the consortium team involved in the activities. Each of the partners have brought specific expertise as well as a broad network and knowledge of connected projects. This has enabled the consortium to have a better understanding of the DIH ecosystem, build a community and offer support to the community. In addition, the DIHNET project has benefitted from well experience Advisory Board and very well-connected Ambassador teams. Last but not least, DIHNET took an open community policy which has allowed us to gather a broad community (over 1500 members) which has been a rich source of information also where the pain and opportunities are for the network, thus guiding the project team in identifying relevant topics.

4 Services to support the network of networks

4.1 Overall introduction of the services of the DIHNET network

As a coordination and support action, the DIHNET project mainly focused on supporting the community of DIHs and EDIHs to enhance their cooperation and alignment and provided various activities to connect and learn from each other. We believe that similar approach should also be followed by a future network. It should be clarified, that the envisioned services target DIHs and DIH networks and related stakeholder. They do not refer to services directly offered to industry (which are usually offered by the DIHs themselves).

Looking at the services and where the DIHs and DIH networks see the most value, we can distinguish among 4 types of services for the support network:

- Ecosystem services: these are the large majority of services, supporting the EU awareness and alignment, building an active and vibrant network.
- Business development services, mainly focused on the support and initiation of collaborations
- Skills development services, which for a EU DIH and network of network approach could focus on three levels – individual improvement/training, community peer learning on EU level and learning from other networks/sectors
- Technology services: while interesting, many of the technology co-development, strategy and standardisation services are offered by thematically focused networks (often led by innovation actions). The role of a network like DIHNET is more horizontal, focusing on facilitating collaborations and connecting with the thematic networks for exchange of information, news, or event train-the-trainer services.

In the next sections, each of these categories is described in more detail.

4.2 Ecosystem development services

The ecosystem development services of (E)DIHs and networks is at the core of the DIHNET and the future network. Looking at the AIDA customer journey (Awareness, Interest, Desire, Action), most of the activities and services in the ecosystem development focus on initiating awareness and interest in the community to engage. Therefore, these are building blocks to support the network and the ecosystem in general.

The revenue streams for ecosystem services are however more limited as they relate to an ecosystem of networks. In our evaluation, we believe that for the DIHNET ecosystem services will mostly rely on revenues related to public funding and some in-kind contribution from the community. While a membership model could be applied in principle, the challenge is that networks like DIHNET are horizontal in nature and this, combined with the many other networks which might depend on memberships, makes the subscription/membership revenue stream for ecosystem support less viable. Public

ecosystem	EU-community building (i.e. community platform, sub-groups, pre-cursor network meetings)
	Support of common (E)DIH strategy development (e.g. Thought-leadership approach, WG discussions)
	Strategic EC advice (e.g. recommendations, DIHNET position papers)
	Collaborative awareness creation (monthly news bulletin, monthly digest from community news, overview of open calls)
	Support of mapping regional capacities/capabilities
	Mapping the ecosystem and promotion (e.g. DIH of the month,)
	Community building events
	Connector to other EU-networks (mapping of related projects and initiatives collection, WGs, etc)

Figure 2: overview of network ecosystem services

funding (e.g. via follow up coordination projects) therefore is at the moment seen as crucial to support the network development on EU level.

Based on the services provided in DIHNET and possible further needs in the ecosystem, the following services are suggested for the network. Many of the services involve different activities, many of which have been tested in the DIHNET project and well-received.

4.3 Business development services

The business development services for DIHNET focus on the development of collaborations and DIH development. Within the DIHNET project, the business-related services focused on the benchmarking activities provided via the Champion Challenge and identification of winners. The future network could further spin to support structural collaborations. As mentioned, another project -BOWI- is currently offering this service but the service is also expected to be supported by the DTA, which is supported to encourage networking and brokerage. These services can be organized on a broad network level (e.g. information and training on steps to develop collaborations, business models, etc) or one-on-one support.

Depending on how the service is further developed, different revenue models are possible: e.g. match fee as well as public funding (e.g. via the DEP).

4.4 Skills development services and resources

Skills relate to the development of the hub, the peer learning activities, including best practices exchange as well as information on skills development (capacities but also offers). So far DIHNET has supported best practices exchange and highlighting some materials from previous DIH training projects (like I4MS, XS2I4MS, SmartFactories, etc). For the future network of (E)DIHs, also peer exchange and train the trainer should also be explored and possibly introduced in a future network.

The skills development services – such as peer learning, train-the-trainer, skills catalogues – are expected to be of interest of both DIHs and networks as well as EU and regional policy makers.

4.5 Technology development services

For a horizontal network of networks like DIHNET, this category is limited in its scope, mostly to activities related to scouting for EU collaborations and possibly organizing train-the-trainer activities also in collaboration with other networks. The technology development services are often addressed by thematic networks and overlap of activities with them should be avoided. One option is for them to be able to provide the technological insights and training to other networks, to ensure higher impact and access to knowledge in Europe. And horizontal networks like DIHNET or the future DTA could be the facilitator, organizer of such an activity.

4.6 Connecting the services and interest from customers

For the future sustainability, we currently see the following interest of different stakeholders per service (see figure below). The assessment is based on the authors experience based on interest shown in the DIHNET activities. This overview allows us to identify which services should be targeted

to which stakeholder group as well as in the future identify possible revenue models and streams per service. The interest in a service does not necessarily correlate with the willingness to pay and revenue models, but provides an indication.

	Service /Interest from stakeholders	(E)DIHs	DIH networks	EC	Networks (non DIH specific)	Regional (policy) stakeholders
ecosystem	EU-community building (i.e. community platform, sub-groups, pre-cursor network meetings)	xx	xxx	xx	x	x
	Support of common (E)DIH strategy development (e.g.Thought-leadership approach, WG discussions)	xx	xx	xx	x	
	Strategic EC advice (e.g. recommendations, DIHNET position papers)	xx	xx	x	x	x
	Collaborative awareness creation (monthly news bulletin, monthly digest from community news, overview of open calls)	x	xx		xx	
	Support of mapping regional capacities/capabilities	xx	xx	xx		x
	Mapping the ecosystem and promotion (e.g. DIH of the month,)	x	x	x		x
	Community building events	xxx	xx	x	xx	x
business	Connector to other EU-networks (mapping of related projects and initiatives collection, WGs, etc)	x	xx	xx	xx	
	Initiating European collaborations	xx	xx	xxx	x	xx
	Support for KPIs and benchmarking of (E)DIHs (e.g. via Champion Challenge)	x		x		
	Support interregional corridors	xx	x	xxx	x	xx

Figure 3: Perceived interest of stakeholders in the ecosystem and business support services

	Service /Interest from stakeholders	(E)DIHs	DIH networks	EC	Networks (non DIH specific)	Regional (policy) stakeholders
Technology	Pan-EU scouting RDI collaborations	xx	x	xxx		x
	Train the trainer for advanced digital technologies	xx	xx	x	xx	x
skills	Organisation EU expert visits/exchange	x	x		x	
	Training of hubs (DIHs Academy - materials from webinars and bus. Model collection from various projects)	xx	x	x	x	
	Organisation pan-EU peer learning (topic specific WG and exchange with other networks)	xx	xx	xxx	xx	x
	Support to share best practices and other information and peer learning	x	x	x	x	x
	Skills information repository	xx	x	xx	x	x

Figure 4: Perceived interest of stakeholders in the technology and skills development services

Based on previous experience in DIHNET, we observe that a wide variety of service need to be offered to satisfy the needs of the different stakeholders. Also, many of the activities can be connected – e.g. community building is interesting for many stakeholders but requires at least some mapping of the ecosystem (which might not always be very attractive for all stakeholders).

5 Possible options to sustain DIHNET project assets and activities

We can see three possible sustainability alternatives for the DIHNET network:

- Continuation of some activities by the future DTA, which is expected to support and coordinate the EDIHs and to a limited extent the DIH ecosystem. Unfortunately, the DTA has not yet started (or call for the project announced).
- (Limited in time) continuation of some element by a partner
- Stopping activities with the end of the DIHNET project
- Establishing a separate entity

Each of these options is further described below with the pro's, con's and some considerations from the DIHNET consortium.

5.1 Setting up a separate association/legal entity

One option, considered by the DIHNET consortium, was whether a separate legal entity (such as an association or non-for-profit organization) could be established and sustained.

The DIHNET project has established a strong brand and significant network of members, which could be used to set up a separate legal entity and continue the network. The DIHNET is recognized in the ecosystem and has managed in the last 3 years to generate interest and establish a position as a though leader in the ecosystem. The brand itself can act as an attractor for further expanding the activities. Yet, the following considerations should also be taken into account:

- (some) Public funding is expected to be needed to support the coordination and support activities of DIHNET
- The upcoming (publicly funded) DTA is expected to also provide many of the activities currently offered by the DIHNET while others could be absorbed by connected networks.
- Membership fees could prove challenging due to the horizontal and quite broad function of the DIHNET and given that many of the members are networks themselves (often publicly funded) and therefore have limited possibility to pay for a membership.

Given the above considerations, currently we do not think a separate entity would be appropriate. It should also be noted that each of the partners of DIHNET will continue with their own activities and developing their expertise.

5.2 DIHNET public materials and deliverables

(selected) Publicly available materials from DIHNET will be included in the [DIHNET website](#) (e.g. champion challenge results, DIH of the month, news, etc) as well as the open access environment [Zenodo](#) to ensure access to key reports, presentations and DIHNET outputs. Key documents can also be referred to the future DTA or interested network.

The DIHNET website will remain open for 5 years but it is not expected that any regular updates on the content will be made after the end of the project. The Zenodo repository is open access repository and as such the DIHNET profile will remain open. The user details have been transferred to TNO. Last but not least, a [info@dihnet.eu](mailto:info@ dihnet.eu) email account was set for the duration of the project. This email address will be closed after December 2021. Reference to project manager and scientific manager contacts is provided on DIHNET website ('contact' section).

Further, the publicly available documents are usually referenced under the EC CORDIS database of project results.

5.3 Invite the DIHNET community to the future DTA community and handover of lessons learnt

As previously mentioned, it is expected that the future DTA will play a significant coordination role in the EU DIH ecosystem. While the DTA will focus on EDIHs, rather than networks or DIH in general, it is expected to initiate the community building, peer exchanges and strategic alignment and support to EDIHs, connect with DIHs as well as establish connections among the EDIHs and strategic networks (e.g. on AI, HPC, cybersecurity) and support EDIHs to provide seamless services with networks like EEN.

As a strategic next network therefore, we can see the following hand over options with the DTA:

- Invite the DIHNET community to the DTA community: once the DTA is selected and starts operations, the DIHNET community can be informed and invited to also join the DTA community. This can be coordinated with the future selected project.
- Additionally, a hand-over meeting can be organized among DIHNET partners and the future DTA (provided there is interest) to highlight some of the DIHNET results and lessons learned, and to guide the consortium to key assets of DIHNET.

5.4 Continuation of the activity led by a partner

The DIHNET project has initiated quite a few activities, seen as adding value to the ecosystem. Some of these activities could be continued by a consortium partner (even if for a limited time). The activities could leverage on the developed brand and expectations from the project. As we are exploring individual activities and assets, the most likely organization of any future activities would be taken up by individual partner per activity with possible limited support from the consortium (e.g. in disseminating in other networks). At the moment, no particular partnership or governance agreements are seen as need. Yet, one of the lessons learned from DIHNET activities is that the network and activities require a dedicated leadership, and as such below we outline possible partner with whom further discussions will be conducted to (temporarily) continue some specific DIHNET topics and activities.

Looking at the DIHNET assets we think there are a few activities to be consider for potential continuation by a partner in DIHNET. The following options are currently considered:

- DIHNET community platform – hosted by FBA – will continue to exist with its current name for at least 6 months after the end of the project (until 30 April 2022). Until this time, limited activation will be conducted by the DIHNET consortium and based on voluntary efforts. FBA will also keep feeding the community with relevant information like news, funding opportunities, etc, based also on participation in other projects. Following this period, FBA will evaluate whether to 1) continue with the community under its brand, 2) transfer/merge it with another FBA community and potentially changing the name, or 3) stop the activity. In any case, the community members will be informed via a message and asked whether they agree for their profiles to be shifted to a (potentially) new community.

- Once the DTA project has been selected, DIHNET community members will be invited to join the DTA community too.
- The DIHNET social media channels will remain open with limited activity and under euRobotics management until the DTA is selected, but for a maximum of up to 6 months after the end of the DIHNET project (30 April). Upon selection of the DTA, social media contacts will be invited to connect to the DTA.
- Thought leadership topics will continue to be developed by the individual partners as part of their separate activities and based on their interest (e.g. via other projects). DIHNET will be ready to discuss with the future DTA or an interested network-of-networks some conclusions of this Thought Leadership approach.
- TNO as a partner in some connected projects will also continue working on selected topics and where relevant publish results or news in the DIHNET community. One example where work will continue in another network is RODIN, where DIHNET and RODIN collaborated on the topic of post-project sustainability of networks and where RODIN has initiated a working group with the involved Innovation Actions. Similarly, BOWI project will continue with its main focus on cross-regional collaboration and results can be shared on the DIHNET community (similar to the joined workshop on the heatmap as a tool to support collaboration).

5.5 Stop activity and engagement

The third option for the post-project plans is to stop activities at the end of the project. While these activities might have added value, other factors such as costs to sustain the activities, connection to the core business of the partners, future outlook of either making the activity self-sustainable or be taken over by another organization need to also be considered. Below we summarize and justify why some of the activities will be stopped:

- The update and evaluation of the JRC Catalogue: the activity will be discontinued on 31 October. In addition, the option for DIHNET to pre-evaluate the DIH submissions will be discontinued and the corresponding tab “DIHNET.eu JRC Catalogue Guidelines/Apply” will be removed. However, the existing materials (webinar and Q&A) instructing and supporting the ecosystem in filling in their profile will remain available in the [DIHNET Community](#).
- The overview of open calls will also be stopped at the end of the project (31 Oct 2021). The DIHNET community will be redirected towards the EC overview of [Competitive calls and calls for third parties](#)
- Monthly digest, news from related initiatives, articles and DIH of the month, WGs: all of these activities were used to activate the ecosystem. With the end of the project, the activities will also be stopped. Yet, partners and members of the community will still have the opportunity to share news and materials via the community platform (see above) based on their own initiative.
- DIHNET webinars and events will also be stopped as these activities are connected to explorative, coordination and thought leadership activities, which are usually more demanding in terms of time and effort. Yet, if a consortium partner wishes to use the DIHNET platform and organize a webinar with DIHNET name attached in the next 6 months, individual agreements with the other partners will be arranged.
- Champion challenge will be stopped. However, the methodology of the champion challenge has been described in the publicly [available D 3.4](#) and announcements in [the DIHNET](#)

[community](#) and [website](#). A similar activity supporting promotion and evaluation of the DIHs is envisioned under the DTA and the DIHNET invites the future DTA consortium to make use of the publicly available methodology of the champion challenge or contact us for clarifications or hand-over conversation.

5.6 Summary and overview of post-project plans for the different assets and activities

Based on the above analysis, the table below summarized the selected option for the main services and assets of DIHNET.

Table 1: Selected option for the main services and assets of DIHNET

Activity	Selected post-project option (continue/stop/transfer to DTA)	Responsible lead partner
DIHNET community platform, incl. established sub-groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - continued for up to 6 months as DIHNET after which FBA will re-evaluate the strategy - FBA will continue to share news and activate the community - minimum activation efforts by DIHNET partners (voluntary basis) 	FBA
DIHNET social media channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Continued for up to 6 months with reduced activity 	euRobotics
Thought leadership topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development based on partner's own activities (continuous research e.g. via other projects) 	Subject to partners own interest, initiative and individual work
Update and evaluation of the JRC Catalogue	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activity will be stopped on 31 Oct. 2021 	n.a.
Overview of open calls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activity will be stopped on 31 Oct. 2021; community is redirected towards EC overview of open calls 	n.a.
Monthly digest, news from related initiatives, articles and DIH of the month, WGs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activity will be stopped on 31 Oct. 2021 	n.a.
DIHNET webinars and events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activity will be stopped on 31 Oct. 2021 	n.a.
Champion challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Activity will be stopped on 31 Oct. 2021; materials from the challenge and results will still be available under the DIHNET community, website and DIHNET deliverable 3.4 	n.a.
DIHNET public deliverables and selected reports/materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All selected materials until the end of the project will be published on the open source ZENODO platform 	Zenodo account details transferred to TNO

6 Conclusions

Based on the analysis above we can conclude that one of the main assets and key to the DIHNET has been the development of an active community. This has been supported by all activities of the DIHNET project. In the process, the DIHNET project has identified that there is a need for a support mechanism in the community that can facilitate networking and collaboration. But a second very relevant element is that there is a need for a strategic vision and an organization that can initiate and lead the discussions on this strategic vision on selected topics. These functions are highly relevant to achieve alignment and stimulate building a cohesive network with more limited overlap. But the connected activities are difficult to sustain on a commercial basis – especially because many of the related 'customers' are at least partially relying on public funding and the cross-network topics are not a cost they can easily transfer to their own customers.

6.1 DIHNET community, brand and communication

Looking at the particular assets and activities, we can conclude that the DIHNET community and informing the network have been in the core of the DIHNET objectives. As a result, FundingBox has agreed to continue the operation of the DIHNET community under the DIHNET brand until the DTA has been selected or up to 6 months after the end of the DIHNET project. In addition, the social media channels (supported by euRobotics) will be preserved (albeit with reduced activity) with the same timeline to continue informing the DIHNET community of relevant events and news until the DTA selection. After this time, the communication channels will be closed and the re-evaluation will be done by FBA whether to continue with the community and the use of the DIHNET brand. Provided that the DTA has been selected in this period, DIHNET community members will also be informed and invited to connect to the DTA.

6.2 Open access to (main) DIHNET outputs and documents

The DIHNET key materials and documents have been published in the DIHNET community and selected items are included in the DIHNET website. However, to ensure access, key documents, deliverables and presentations have been selected and published in Zenodo open access database.

6.3 Hand-over lessons learned to DTA and reference of the community

DIHNET is open to discuss with future networks some of the project conclusions and lessons learned. Particularly, anticipating the importance of the future DTA, the DIHNET consortium is happy to participate in a meeting to share some of the lessons learned and key take-aways. Also, provided that the DTA is running within 6 months of the end of DIHNET, the members of the community will be informed of the DTA and invited to connect to them.